

MODELLING OF ENVIRONMENTALLY INDUCED DAMAGE IN POLYMER MATRIX COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY: An investigation has been performed into the behavior of composite laminates exposed to severe environmental conditions. Given material properties, laminate geometry and specified cyclical thermal and moisture environments, a model predicts absorbed moisture, chemical degradation, and stresses in the laminate as functions of position and time. A simplified solution allows very efficient calculations for large numbers of complex thermal and moisture cycles. Cases relevant to the proposed High Speed Civil Transport show two types of moisture absorption behavior: rapid fluctuation of levels near the surface, and gradual settling to an easily computed equilibrium value in the interior. Chemical degradation is (based on preliminary, parametric calculations) shown to be a concern for surface plies. Stress levels due to these effects will enhance damage in surface plies. Stress effects do not fully account for observed moisture induced damage, suggesting material property changes or enhanced cracking mechanisms.

KEYWORDS: moisture, degradation, analysis, cyclic exposure, environmental effects, hygral stresses, thermal stresses, damage

INTRODUCTION

Aircraft systems such as the proposed High Speed Civil Transport (HSCT) experience severe cyclic environments during normal operations. Aircraft skins reach extreme temperatures due to high vehicle speeds; diffusion of moisture and oxygen into the material is accelerated by these temperatures; these in turn can cause property changes and/or permanent material degradation. An example exposure cycle with time-dependent temperature and moisture levels is shown below. This is a test cycle; similar cycles may be repeated over 20,000 times in an aircraft lifetime. Under such conditions, thermal, hygral, and chemical degradation effects result in a complex and time-varying stress profile over the course of many experimental or use cycles.

A set of models and computer codes has been developed to aid in the calculation of severe environmental effects. Using as inputs ambient temperature, relative humidity (RH), oxidative environment, material properties and laminate geometry, the codes predict the material state, degraded properties, and resulting stress state as functions of position and time.

Fig. 1: Sample environmental test profile

BACKGROUND

The influence of environmental effects on composite structures has received a great deal of attention in the literature. Investigators have attempted to decouple temperature, moisture and chemical effects [1-5] as well as analyze the interactions during combined exposure [6-11].

A good development of the behavior of a substance diffusing into another is given by Crank [12] and expanded by Springer [2] and Tsai and Hahn [3]. For a limited range of environmental conditions, moisture sorption follows Fickian behavior. Moisture sorption in to a laminate has a much slower diffusion rate than does temperature ($\sim 10^6$ times slower). For this reason the laminate response to temperature change is often considered instantaneous and constant across a laminate's thickness. Theories have been developed to account for the coupled distributions of moisture and temperature [13]. Several mathematical formulations have been developed in order to simplify the calculations required for predicting moisture sorption. Springer's "W8GAIN" model was developed in 1981 in order to predict the distribution of moisture and temperature in a laminate exposed to wet conditions [14], and Weitsman developed a code (also in 1981) that searched for the most efficient calculation for moisture sorption in a laminate over time periods with fluctuating ambient conditions [7].

Chemical changes in composite materials attributed to environmental exposure are less well understood than moisture effects. Several distinguishing characteristics mark chemical degradation: discoloration and embrittlement of the surface; weight loss; decrease of material strength; and microcracking. Recently, much work has been done to characterize the reactions occurring in the polymer in an attempt to understand these changes [4,5,15].

Calculations of stresses resulting from temperature, moisture, and degradation states in the material is common in the literature via micromechanics and composite laminated plate theory (CLPT). Tensile residual stresses that are inherent in general composite laminates after cool-down from cure temperature (due to ply coefficient of thermal expansion mismatch) may be at least partially relieved by moisture-induced stresses (resulting from swelling of the laminate) [16]. Chemical degradation adds complexity, altering the material properties at the exposed surface. The potential for microcracking damage is high during

cyclic environmental exposure [17-19,9]. Microcracking has been seen to increase the diffusion rate of moisture [20,21,6] resulting in non-Fickian sorption behavior.

MODEL DEVELOPMENT

A code was developed in order to characterize the state of a material exposed cyclically in air to an environmental profile in which temperature and moisture vary with time. User defined inputs include this profile, relevant material properties, laminate geometry and number of cycles.

It is assumed that an infinite plate is exposed to uniform environmental conditioning on its top and bottom surfaces ($z=0$ and $z=h$). Diffusion is assumed to be one-dimensional through the thickness (the z direction). Temperature is constant through the thickness, and instantaneously equal to the time-varying ambient temperature.

Moisture Sorption

It is assumed that moisture and oxygen diffuse into the material following a one-dimensional Fickian law. Outlined below is the development for moisture; the reasoning for oxygen diffusion is similar. Fick's Law is given by:

$$\frac{\partial C}{\partial t} = D \frac{\partial^2 C}{\partial z^2} \quad (1)$$

where C is the concentration of moisture in the laminate, z is the through thickness direction, and D is the diffusion rate. The diffusion rate is dependent on the diffusion constant, D_0 , activation energy, E_A , gas constant, R , and absolute temperature, T [12]:

$$D = D_0 \exp\left[\frac{-E_A}{RT}\right] \quad (2)$$

Initial and boundary are required to solve Eqn 1. These are given below:

$$\text{for } t < 0 \quad C(z) = C_0(z) \quad (3)$$

$$\text{for } t > 0 \quad C(0) = C_\infty(t) \quad , \quad C(h) = C_\infty(t) \quad (4)$$

The value $C_0(z)$ is simply the initial state of moisture through the laminate. The quantity $C_\infty(t)$ represents the concentration at the surface. At every instant of exposure, the surface of the laminate is assumed to be saturated at the level corresponding to the current atmospheric relative humidity. Saturation level is a function of relative humidity, Φ , and material constants a and B , which must be determined empirically [2].

$$C_\infty = a(\Phi)^B \quad (5)$$

An efficient solution to the above problem is needed to compute moisture and oxygen levels in structures undergoing large numbers of complex thermal and environmental profiles. Here, profiles including relative humidities that remain constant over specified lengths of time (Fig. 2a) and temperatures that remain constant or change at a constant rate (Fig. 2b) are considered. Such profiles can be repeated an arbitrary number of times.

Fig. 2a: Possible moisture profile

Fig. 2b: Possible temperature profile

A modal solution of Eqn 1 in the time interval starting at t_{i-1} is:

$$C(z,t) = C_{\infty i} - \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} A_{ni} \sin\left(\frac{n\pi z}{h}\right) \exp\left[\frac{-n^2 \pi^2 D \Delta t}{h^2}\right] \quad (6)$$

where the change in time $\Delta t = t - t_{i-1}$, and C_{-i} is calculated from Φ_i using Eqn 5. In Eqn 6, A_{ni} represents the amplitude of each mode calculated from the concentration at time t_{i-1} , and n is the index of each mode. In order to find the first set of modal amplitudes from the initial conditions, we make use of a Fourier series expansion [22].

$$A_{n1} = \frac{2}{h} \int_0^h (C_{\infty 1} - C_0(z)) \sin\left(\frac{n\pi z}{h}\right) dz \quad (7)$$

where the subscript 1 represents values at the first time step ($i=1$). We can therefore perform the first set of calculations for A_{ni} , and use these values in Eqn 6 to find the concentration levels, $C(z,t)$. In order to calculate subsequent modal amplitudes, $A_{n(i+1)}$, and thus new concentrations, we substitute $C(z,t_i)$ (from Eqn 6) for $C_0(z)$, and $C_{-(i+1)}$ for C_{-1} , in Eqn 7, simplify, integrate, and exploit the orthogonality of the sine function to get the general form:

$$A_{n(i+1)} = \frac{4}{n\pi} (C_{\infty(i+1)} - C_{\infty i}) + A_{ni} \exp\left(\frac{-n^2 \pi^2 D \Delta t_i}{h^2}\right) \quad (8)$$

where $\Delta t_i = t_i - t_{i-1}$. For the geometry of interest only odd values of n need to be calculated. This form is useful in that it does not require the evaluation of integrals of the form of Eqn 7 except at the initial time step.

The previous development is appropriate for periods of constant temperature, as the moisture diffusivity, D , is constant, and can be calculated via Eqn 2. For the segments with changing temperatures, however, this calculation is complicated by the time dependence of temperature. The resulting variation in D invalidates the solutions above. This problem is solved by substituting Eqn 2 into Eqn 6 and defining a modified time step, Δt^* . This yields an equation for the calculation of the current moisture concentration during a temperature ramp:

$$C(z,t) = C_{\infty i} - \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} A_{ni} \sin\left(\frac{n\pi z}{h}\right) \exp\left[\frac{-n^2\pi^2 D_o \Delta t^*}{h^2}\right] \quad (9)$$

where

$$\Delta t^* = \int_{t_{i-1}}^t \exp\left[\frac{-E_A}{RT(t)}\right] dt \quad (10)$$

If the moisture and temperature profiles are repeated (cycled), we can calculate the values of Δt_i^* for each segment prior to doing the cyclical calculations

$$\Delta t_i^* = \int_{t_{i-1}}^{t_i} \exp\left[\frac{-E_A}{RT(t)}\right] dt \quad (11)$$

and Eqn 8 becomes

$$A_{n(i+1)} = \frac{4}{n\pi} (C_{\infty(i+1)} - C_{\infty i}) + A_{ni} \exp\left(\frac{-n^2\pi^2 D_o \Delta t_i^*}{h^2}\right) \quad (12)$$

This allows easy calculation of moisture concentrations for each segment. The coefficients A_{ni} are found by progressive application of Eqn 12, and then the concentration at any time can be found from Eqn. 9. The calculations are repeated for as many cycles as needed.

Oxidative Degradation

The same scheme outlined above is used to calculate the diffusion of oxygen into the laminate. Once the local oxygen concentration is calculated, both thermal and oxidative reactions altering the polymer structure in the laminate are calculated via the method outlined by Cunningham and McManus [15]. The resulting output is in the form of a dimensionless metric, b , of the reaction process that is related to material mass loss. This metric is referred to below as the level of completeness of the reaction, reaching a value of one when all of the available material has been chemically degraded.

Stress Predictions

Varying thermal conditions, absorbed moisture, and chemical degradation of the material all affect the stress state in the structure. The resulting stress state in the laminate can be computed by including the environmental effects in a constitutive equation [24]:

$$\sigma_{ij} = E_{ijkl}(T, C, b)[\varepsilon_{kl} - \alpha_{kl}\Delta T - \beta_{kl}\Delta C - \chi_{kl}b] \quad (13)$$

In Eqn 13, Young's modulus, E , is dependent on the current temperature, T , the moisture concentration, C , and the chemical state, b . The coefficients of thermal and moisture expansion (α and β respectively) determine material expansion due to changes in temperature, ΔT , from the stress free temperature, T_0 , and changes in moisture level from the

dry condition. The degradative effects are treated in much the same way, with χ representing the coefficients of degradation induced expansion or shrinkage. This equation can be used in conjunction with composite laminate plate theory (CLPT) to determine stresses in each ply. An available code capable of handling all of the above effects, a modification of the Integrated Composites Analyzer (ICAN) [24], was used to do these calculations.

ANALYSIS

Material properties for IM7/PETI-5 were supplied by the Boeing Company and McDonnell Douglas Aircraft [23]. Properties relating to moisture and oxygen diffusivity were approximated from values of similar materials (primarily C6000/PMR-15). Calculations were done using values from Table 1, along with oxygen diffusion and reaction values from [15].

Table 1: Properties used

E_{11} GPa (ksi)	E_{22} GPa (ksi)	G_{12} GPa (ksi)	ν_{12}	G_{IC} J/m ² (Btu/in ²)	ρ kg/m ³ (lb/in ³)	X_t MPa (ksi)	X_c MPa (ksi)	Y_t MPa (ksi)	Y_c MPa (ksi)	S MPa (ksi)
157.3 (22.8)	9.7 (1.4)	4.20 (0.6)	0.3 3	1000 (6x10 ⁻¹)	1600 (0.06)	2160 (310)	1560 (230)	70 (10)	150 (22)	80 (12)

α_{11} $\mu\epsilon/K$	α_{22} $\mu\epsilon/K$	k_1 W/m ² K	k_2 W/m ² K	D_o mm ² /s	E_A kJ/mol	a	B	T_o (°F)
-0.7	36.9	8.65	0.35	0.8	42	0.018	1	600

Results of some sample runs of the codes, using the material described above, in sixteen ply laminates of unidirectional ([0]₁₆) or quasi-isotropic ([0 \pm 45/90]_{2s}) lay-up, exposed to up to 5000 of the cycles shown in Fig. 1, are depicted in the following figures. Moisture levels are given as fractions of dry weights, which reach a maximum at 0.0153 (1.53%) for a RH level of 85% (see Eqn 5). The initial moisture condition is specified as either dry ($C_0 = 0$) or saturated at 85% RH ($C_0 = 0.0153$).

RESULTS

Results are presented in terms of time histories at specific locations, or profiles at specific times. Times are specified by cycles elapsed, and select times within a cycle are noted by the designations t_A , t_B , and t_C from Fig. 1.

Cyclic moisture exposure causes two types of response under the conditions studied. The first is vacillation of the moisture at the surface (shown in both Figures 3a and 3b). The first time, t_A , designates the time just after cold, dry exposure. Due to the dry atmosphere, the very edge of the laminate dries out. However, little moisture diffuses out at this low temperature in the given amount of time. The hot, dry exposure just before t_B allows moisture near the surface to dry almost completely. The t_C marker designates the period just after the warm, wet exposure, when the surface is saturated. Comparison of Figures 3a and 3b shows that moisture level fluctuation near the surface continues relatively unchanged with each cycle. The second type of response is the slow soak of moisture in towards the center of the

laminates. This internal behavior does not respond to the cycling; instead, we can observe a gradual change from cycle 2 (Fig. 3a) to cycle 100 (Fig. 3b).

Figure 4 shows a different perspective on these effects. Full time histories at different points in the material are shown. At the edge of the laminate, oscillations of the moisture is evident. The sharp rises and falls in moisture levels at the edges are a result of the boundary condition defined earlier: the surface is always saturated at the current ambient humidity. At one ply thickness into the laminate, there are significant fluctuations in moisture level throughout each cycle. At the center of the laminate, the slow change of moisture level can be seen.

Fig. 3: Snapshot of moisture levels at points in cycle 2 (a) and cycle 100 (b)

In Fig. 5, the slow change in the center of the laminate over many cycles is shown more clearly. Experimental values based on weight change measurements during hygrothermal cycles are from reference [23]. The moisture content equilibrates at some non-zero level. Plots of the through-thickness moisture levels at distinct points in many cycles show this same trend. Figure 6 shows concentration profiles at time t_B in a 16 ply laminate over the course of 100 cycles for two different initial conditions.

Fig. 4: Moisture fluctuations at various points in laminate

Fig. 5: Predicted and experimental moisture levels at center of a 16 ply laminate exposed to 200 cycles (a) dry initially, and (b) saturated, then exposed

Fig. 6: Moisture level through thickness of 16 ply laminate at t_b in multi-cycle run (a) dry initially, and (b) saturated, then exposed

Output from different conditions (varying laminate thicknesses and initial conditions) show similar equilibrium values in the center of the laminate. This value may be calculated using the Eqn 14. It is simply a diffusion rate weighted average of the environmental conditions, and agrees with both values predicted by the full analyses and experimental data. The value predicted for the cycle shown in Fig. 1 and the material described in Table 1 is 0.18%.

$$C_{eq} = \frac{\int_{cycle} C_{\infty} \exp\left[\frac{-E_A}{RT}\right] dt}{\int_{cycle} \exp\left[\frac{-E_A}{RT}\right] dt} \quad (14)$$

Chemical Degradation

The conditions of the cycle in Fig. 1 result in minimal chemical changes, using the values of oxygen diffusion and reaction chemistry given in [15]. As these are for PMR-15 material, the possibility that the PETI-5 material may be more susceptible to degradation was explored. Calculations were done with the same material values, but the original profile accelerated in terms of temperature and time of exposure. The maximum temperature was 475° F (replacing

the 350° F segment in the cycle in Fig. 1), which was held for 2.5 hours (compared with 30 minutes in the original). When the model was run simulating a 5000 cycle exposure, the degradation shown in Figures 7 and 8 resulted. After one thousand cycles, there is non-trivial degradation occurring at the surface. Such degradation is observed as a visible surface layer. This layer has been seen to correspond with altered material properties [4,5]. After as many as five thousand cycles, the degradation has begun to grow toward the interior of the laminate.

Fig. 7: Completeness of reactions in 8 ply laminate exposed to an extreme cycle

Fig. 8: Total mass lost in laminate over 5000 cycles

Stress States

Calculated stresses are shown as functions of position through the laminate under various conditions. Only the stresses locally perpendicular to the fibers are shown as these are the stresses primarily responsible for microcracking. The matrix materials proposed for this project have very high cure temperatures, resulting in large thermal stresses in the quasi-isotropic ($[0/\pm 45/90]_{2s}$) laminates. Thermal stresses resulting from the profile depicted in Fig. 1 range from approximately 3 ksi to 10 ksi.

In Fig. 9, stresses due solely to moisture sorption are shown. This laminate has been left in a wet environment long enough to reach saturation, and subsequently cycled. As it begins the cycle, the external plies dry out first. The notable result of the hygral stresses in this example is the large gradient between the outer plies (loaded in tension) and the internal plies (loaded in compression). Figure 10 shows the stress field due to degradation at five thousand of the higher temperature, extended time cycles. Stresses reach large tensile values near the surface.

Fig. 9: Stress due to moisture only in 16 ply laminates

Fig. 10: Stress due to degradation only in 16 ply laminates

CONCLUSIONS

A computationally efficient model has been developed for computing the response of composite laminates to hygro-thermal cycling. This model predicts two significant effects of cyclic moisture absorption: large fluctuations in absorbed moisture level at the material surface due to changing ambient conditions; and a slow increase in the interior of the laminate to an equilibrium level. This equilibrium level can be calculated easily using a simple temperature-weighted average of the environmental conditions. The moisture absorption results agree with experimentally measured moisture gains.

Sample problems suggest that the environmentally-induced stress state is determined primarily by thermal stresses. If degradation takes place, it will result in significantly enhanced stresses near the surface. This could explain the surface microcracking observed in numerous studies [4,5,11,13,15,18,19]. The moisture stresses, though smaller in magnitude, are non-trivial and can induce stress gradients through the thickness. The worst case hygral stresses are on the same order of magnitude as the thermal stresses. In particular, moisture stresses can be severe in unidirectional laminates undergoing dry-out from a saturated condition. The computed stresses do not fully explain the increased cracking observed under exposure to moisture [6,8,10,17,18,20], suggesting that there are mechanisms for moisture-induced cracking beyond moisture-induced stresses. The presence of moisture in the laminate could cause temporary or permanent changes in material properties, in particular the transverse fracture toughness, or it could enhance the cracking mechanisms in ways not yet understood.

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REFERENCES

1. Shen, C.H. and G.S. Springer, "Moisture Absorption and Desorption of Composite Materials," *J. Composite Materials*, Vol. 10, No. 1, 1976, pp. 2-20.
2. Springer, G.S., "Environmental Effects," *Composites Design*, 4th Ed., S. Tsai, ed., Think Composites, Dayton, Ohio, 1988, pp. 16-1 to 16-18.
3. Tsai, S.W, and H.T. Hahn, *Introduction to Composite Materials*, Technomic Publishing, Lancaster PA, 1980.
4. Bowles, K.J., "A Thermally Modified Polymer Matrix Composite Material with Structural Integrity to 371°C," *Proceedings Twentieth SAMPE Technical Conference*, Minneapolis, MN, Sept, 1988.
5. Roberts, G.D. and R.D. Vannucci, "Effect of Solution Concentration and Aging Conditions on PMR-15 Resins," *SAMPE Journal*, Mar/Apr 1986, pp. 24-28.

6. Burcham, L.J., M.R. VanLandingham, R.F. Eduljee, and J.W. Gillespie, "Moisture Effects on the Material Behavior of Graphite Polyimide Composites," *Proceedings Ninth International conference on Composite Materials*, Newark, DE, Sept, 1994.
7. Weitsman, Y. "A Rapidly Convergent Scheme to Compute Moisture Profiles in Composite Materials under Fluctuating Ambient Conditions," *J. Composite Materials*, Vol. 15, No. 7, 1981, pp. 349-358.
8. Beckwith, S.W. and B.D. Wallace, "Effects of Aging and Environmental Conditions on Kevlar/Epoxy Composites," *SAMPE Quarterly*, Vol. 14, No.6, July, 1983.
9. Upadhyay, P.C. and J. Prucz, "Parametric Damage Modeling of Composites due to Moisture Absorption," *J. of Reinforced Plastics and Composites*, Vol. 11, 1992, pp. 198-210.
10. Whiteside, J.B., R.J. DeIasi, and R.L. Schulte, "Distribution of Absorbed Moisture in Graphite/Epoxy Laminates After Real-Time Environmental Cycling," *Long Term Behavior of Composites, ASTM STP 813*, O'Brien, T.K., Ed., American Society for Testing and Materials, Philadelphia, 1983, pp. 192-205.
11. Ming, L, "The Environmental Effects of Carbon Fiber Reinforced Polyethersulphone Composites," *Proceedings Tenth International Conference on Composite Materials*, Whistler, B.C., Canada, August, 1995, pp. 297-303.
12. Crank, J., *The Mathematics of Diffusion*, 2nd Ed., Clarendon Press, Oxford, England, 1975.
13. Chang, W-J., T-C. Chen, and C-I. Weng, "Transient Hygrothermal Stresses in an Infinitely Long Annular Cylinder," *J. of Thermal Stresses*, Vol. 14, 1991, pp. 439-454.
14. Springer, G.S. *Environmental Effects on Composite Materials*, Technomic Publishing, Lancaster, PA, Vols.1 and 2, 1981.
15. Cunningham, R. and McManus, H., "Coupled Diffusion-Reaction Models for Predicting the Distribution of Degradation in Polymer Matrix Composites," Presented at the 1996 ASME International Mechanical Engineering Congress and Exposition Atlanta, GA, Nov. 1996.
16. Chamis, C.C., "Simplified Composite Micromechanics Equations for Hygral, Thermal and Mechanical Properties," *SAMPE Quarterly*, April, 1984, pp. 14-23.
17. Mandell, J.F., "Origin of Moisture Effects on Crack Propagation in Composites," Dept. of Materials Science and Engineering Research Report R77-4, Massachusetts Institute of Technology, Dec. 1977.
18. Martin, R.H., E.J. Siochi and T.S. Gates, "Isothermal Aging of IM7/8320 and IM7/5260," Presented at the 7th Technical Conference on Composite Materials, The Pennsylvania State University, University Park, PA, October, 1992.

19. Chester, R.J, and A.A. Baker, "Environmental Durability of F/A-18 Gr/Ep Composites," *Proceedings Tenth International Conference on Composite Materials*, Whistler, B.C., Canada, August, 1995, pp. 239-246.
20. Lucas, J.P. and J. Zhou, "Moisture Interaction Characteristics and Fracture in Polymer Composites," *Proceedings Tenth International Conference on Composite Materials*, Whistler, B.C., Canada, August, 1995, pp. 247-256.
21. Cai, L.-W. and Y. Weitsman, "Non-Fickian Moisture Diffusion in Polymeric Composites," *J. Composite Materials*, Vol. 28, No.2, 1994, pp. 130-154.
22. Hildebrand, F.B. *Advanced Calculus for Applications*, Englewood Cliffs, N.J.: Prentice-Hall, 1976.
23. Zabora, R. Personal correspondence, July and September, 1996.
24. McManus, H.L. and C. Chamis, "Stress and Damage in Polymer Matrix Composite Materials Due to Material Degradation at High Temperatures," *NASA TM 4682*, January, 1996.